

Architectural Tactics in Software Architecture: A Systematic Mapping Study (Study protocol)

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1 Background

Interest in architectural tactics has grown significantly over the years in the software architecture community. In this regard, the Software Engineering Institute (SEI) has been relevant when it comes to the investigation of architectural tactics. Initially discussed in technical reports [1], architectural tactics were introduced to support understanding the relationship between quality attribute requirements and architecture design. SEI introduced the concept of the general scenario as a precise and independent mechanism for specifying quality attribute requirements [4]. In this context, the idea of architectural tactics emerged, whose initial objective was to represent the characterization of architecture decisions that are used to achieve a quality attribute. Additionally, architecture tactics were used to satisfy response measures based on quality attributes concerning quality models.

On the other hand, the interest in architectural tactics has also yielded that the original definition of architectural tactics has had to evolve in order to address design decisions in other emerging domains such as cloud [14], cyber-foraging [8] and cyber-security [16]. Nevertheless, this evolution of architectural tactics has implied that information about how they are identified, the mechanisms for describing them and the data sources used to recognize them is increasingly unknown. This causes a lack of explicit knowledge about the fundamentals of architectural tactics in these emerging domains, which limits the systematic replication of the characterization of new architectural tactics to address design decisions in modern systems. The definition and description of architectural tactics taxonomies presented in [3] address seven quality attributes; however, there is little research on which quality attributes have been addressed by architectural tactics research. This implies that it is unclear whether the architectural tactics community has maintained an interest in these seven quality attributes or has addressed others. Moreover, there is not enough research that systematically compiles updates or new proposals for architectural tactics taxonomies.

This paper describes the literature review protocol we have executed for the article *Architectural Tactics in Software Architecture: A systematic Mapping Study*. The steps described in this protocol allow us to collect, characterize and describe the primary studies investigating architectural tactics. The contribution of this protocol is the replicability of our study in order to enrich the results obtained.

1.1 Related work

Previous studies have revised the tactics literature with specific quality attributes or technologies in mind.

Lewis et al. [8] conducted a systematic literature mapping of tactics for cyber-foraging, arguing that mobile devices have become the dominant way to interact with the Internet, businesses, and social networks. The study

describes quality attributes that are relevant for cyber-foraging systems, and found research gaps regarding system-level concerns for operations in cyber-foraging systems and large-scale evaluations. As a further result, they codified design decisions and proposed tactics for cyber-foraging.

Ullah et al. [16] conducted a systematic study of tactics for Big Data Cyber-security Analytics (BDCA) systems. They described critical quality attributes for BDCA systems (namely, performance, accuracy, and scalability), and found a lack of architectural support for some of them. They also remarked the lack of empirical research about the coding of tactics and quality trade-offs among tactics.

Li et al. [9] reported a systematic literature review for microservice architectures. They identified six key quality attributes for microservices architecture (namely, scalability, performance, availability, monitorability, security, and testability), and proposed nineteen tactics to address them.

In the same line, Osses et al. [10] also explored tactics and architectural patterns for microservice architectures, and concluded that there is actual but scant evidence of tactics in microservice architectures.

Paradis et al. [11] explored tactics for energy efficiency. They proposed a new taxonomy for energy efficiency to address the identified research gaps; discussed evidence from industry regarding the use of tactics for software energy efficiency; and argued for the need of experimental studies to validate these tactics.

While these studies agree on the relevance and importance of architectural tactics to address quality attributes, they all focus on specific domains or types of systems. This study has explored tactics more broadly rather than for specific domains, and has done so by mapping how the literature has addressed the various aspects of tactics.

2 Systematic study process

This section describes the process conducted in this SMS (see Figure 1). Inspired by the systematic literature mapping process proposed by [12], our process mainly includes activities that focus on (i) search and selection of studies, (ii) data extraction and (iii) synthesis and classification of studies. Additionally, we include a snowballing process [18] to identify further studies.

Figure 1: Design and execution summary of the systematic mapping study

2.1 Research objective

The study objective is to identify, analyze, evaluate, and interpret the body of knowledge on architectural tactics. We focused on conducting a comprehensive review of academic studies to characterize the contributions of tactics in the discipline of software architecture.

2.2 Research questions

To illustrate the contribution of tactics, the study addresses five research questions:

Research question 1 (RQ1)

Which quality attributes have been addressed by architectural tactics research?

Objective: This research question aims to explore the quality attributes that have been studied by tactics research studies and describe the role and purpose of tactics in the studies in order to illustrate their contribution.

Research question 2 (RQ2)

Which techniques have been proposed to identify architectural tactics?

Objective: This research question intends to show and describe the main techniques primary studies use to identify tactics. Additionally, this research question aims to discuss why the studies use the identified techniques.

Research question 3 (RQ3)

Which kinds of data sources are used to recognize architectural tactics?

Objective: The purpose of this research question is to identify and describe the most popular data sources used by studies to recognize tactics in order to analyze the motivation and rationale of studies to use the identified data sources.

Research question 4 (RQ4)

What mechanisms are used to describe architectural tactics?

Objective: This research question aims to identify and describe the mechanisms used by primary studies to describe tactics, as well as the variables, rationale, or aspects used by researchers for the description.

Research question 5 (RQ5)

Which taxonomies of architectural tactics have been proposed or updated?

Objective: Based on the taxonomies of tactics originally described in [2], the purpose of this research is to detail which taxonomies have been updated or proposed in research studies, as well as the corresponding motivation for this.

2.3 Study search

We defined the search string using the P.I.C.O. (Population, Intervention, Comparison, Outcomes) approach proposed by Kitchenham *et al.* [6]. As we are conducting an SMS, we focused only on Population and Intervention, as suggested by Petersen *et al.* [12] [13].

- *Population*: Studies related to software architecture.
- *Intervention*: Architectural tactics.

For each strategy, we defined keywords and defined the search string, which is (“software” OR “architecture”) AND “architectural” AND “tactic*”. Having defined the search string, we searched for primary studies in electronic databases (see Table 1) and we focused on the title and keywords of each paper. For each database consulted, the search string was adapted using the specific standards of each database. For each study, we reviewed the title and abstract in order to understand the proposal of each paper.

Table 1: Databases consulted

Name	URL
IEEE Xplore	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/Xplore/home.jsp
SpringerLink	https://link.springer.com
Scopus	https://www.scopus.com
ACM Library	https://dl.acm.org
Web of Science	http://login.webofknowledge.com
ScienceDirect	https://www.sciencedirect.com
Wiley	https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com

Since each database has its own search procedure, Figures 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, and 8 describes the search string in each database described in Table 1.

[All: software] OR [All: architecture]] AND [All: architectural] AND [All: tactic*]

Figure 2: Query executed in ACM Digital library

("All Metadata":software) OR ("All Metadata":architecture) AND ("All Metadata":architectural) AND ("All Metadata":tactic*) ×

Figure 3: Query executed in IEEE Xplore

Find articles with these terms

(software OR architecture) AND architectural AND tactic

Figure 4: Query executed in ScienceDirect

("software" OR "architecture") AND "architectural" AND "tactic*"

 Set alert

Figure 5: Query executed in Scopus

'(software OR architecture) AND architectural AND tactic*'

Figure 6: Query executed in SpringerLink

Query Preview

((ALL=(software)) OR ALL=(architecture)) AND ALL=(architectural)) AND ALL=(tactic*)

+ Add date range

× Clear

Search ▾

Figure 7: Query executed in Web of Science

"(software OR architecture) AND architectural AND tactic*"

Figure 8: Query executed in Wiley

Once the first set of primary studies was obtained, we stored the papers using Reference Management Software¹ to support the search for primary studies.

2.4 Research team

The research team is composed of the following people:

- *Principal researcher*: Gastón Márquez, Universidad Técnica Federico Santa María, Concepción, Chile. He conducts the systematic literature review and executes the steps described in the protocol.
- *Senior researcher*: Hernán Astudillo, Universidad Técnica Federico Santa María, Santiago, Chile. He supports the review and selection of the primary studies. He makes sure that all steps of the protocol

¹For this SMS, we used Mendeley (<https://www.mendeley.com>)

are executed correctly. In addition, he supports the systematic analysis of the primary studies in order to extract and characterize knowledge.

- *Advisor*: Rick Kazman, University of Hawaii, Hawaii, USA. He is a leading researcher in the software architecture community. Author of several books and articles related to software architecture and architecture tactics, he helps to analyze and discuss the results obtained in order to make decisions about what to include in the article.

2.5 Study selection

To select the articles, we executed the following filters:

- *First filter*: We scrutinized for the keywords of the search string in each article abstract. If the keywords were not found in the abstract, the article was omitted. In this filter, we also removed duplicate articles.
- *Second filter*: We applied the inclusion and exclusion criteria. Any irrelevant articles were omitted at this stage. We defined the following inclusion and exclusion criteria:
 - Inclusion criteria
 - * The study should address tactics research topics.
 - * The study should focus on tactics in software architecture research.
 - * The study should be subject to peer review.
 - * The study must be written in English.
 - Exclusion criteria
 - * Secondary studies
 - * Studies that used “tactics” as technological innovation strategies, rules, algorithms and marketing strategy.
 - * Grey literature.
 - * Short studies (< 4 pages).
 - * Studies in poster format, tutorials, editorials, etc.

One author executed the inclusion and exclusion criteria. Subsequently, two authors reviewed the final set of primary studies to mitigate any potential bias, and hence a threat to validity.

- *Third filter*: From the remaining set of articles we read the abstract again, the introduction and conclusion. In this step, we omitted those articles whose abstract does not appropriately represent what was described in the introduction and conclusion.

2.6 Snowballing process

To explore more primary studies, we executed a snowballing method [18]. This method is a non-probabilistic (non-random) sampling used when the information in the samples (primary studies) is difficult to find. The main characteristic of snowballing is the use of initial primary studies to generate additional studies. For this SMS, we used this method in order to increase the search scope for primary studies. We performed backward and forward snowballing procedures (i.e. references and citations), using Google Scholar².

2.7 Data extraction

To extract the primary studies data, we created a template to organize the information (see Table 2). One author conducted the data extraction, and a second author verified the extracted information.

2.8 Data analysis and classification

The information extracted from the primary studies was grouped, extracted and tabulated in the template described in Table 2. Items I1 through I8 correspond to the demographic data from the primary studies. Item I7 categorizes the studies based on the research type. For this classification, we used the proposal of Wieringa et al. [17], which classifies studies based on the following categories:

- *Evaluation research*: This type of study deals with investigating a practical problem or the implementation of a technique in practice.
- *Proposal of solution*: These studies propose a solution or technique and argue about its relevance, without exhaustive validation.

²<https://scholar.google.com>

Table 2: Data extraction template

Item	Data item	Description	RQ
I1	ID	Unique study identifier	Demographics
I2	Authors	Name of the authors.	
I3	Title	Study title.	
I4	Venue	Name of the journal, conference, workshop, symposium or book where the primary study was published.	
I5	Type venue	Categorization of the venue: journal, conference, workshop, symposium or book chapter.	
I6	Year	Publication year.	
I7	Research type	Classification of studies by research type (see Section 2.8 for more details).	
I8	Study contribution	Classification of studies by contribution type (see Section 2.8 for more details).	
I9	Quality attributes	Description of the quality attributes addressed by the primary studies.	RQ1
I10	Technique/method	Detail of the techniques and methods used to identify architectural tactics.	RQ2
I11	Data source	Description of the data source used by the primary studies to recognize tactics.	RQ3
I12	Criteria	Identification of criteria to characterize tactics.	RQ4
I13	Taxonomy	Identification of new or updated tactics taxonomies.	RQ5

- *Validation research*: These studies investigate the properties of a proposed solution that has not yet been implemented in practice.
- *Philosophical papers*: This type of study outlines a new way of looking at things, a new conceptual framework, etc.
- *Opinion papers*: These studies emphasize the authors’ opinion about what is right or wrong about something, how something should be done, etc.
- *Personal experience papers*: These studies emphasize the *what* rather than the *why*; may relate to one or more projects, but part of the author’s personal experience.

According to [12], the classification proposed by Wieringa et al. describes the research facet of primary studies, reflecting the research approach used in the papers. Furthermore, this classification is easy to interpret and use without evaluating each paper in particular.

Regarding I8, we followed Kuhrmann et al. [7] (inspired by Shaw’s classification of research results [15]) to classify the contributions of primary studies as follow:

- *Model*: Representation of a reality observed by concepts related to tactics.
- *Theory*: Construct of cause-effect relationships.
- *Framework*: Framework or method related to tactics.
- *Guidelines*: List of suggestions regarding the use of tactics.
- *Lessons learned*: Set of outputs from results obtained in empirical studies related to tactics.
- *Advice*: Recommendations about the use or experiences of tactics
- *Tool*: A tool that uses tactics for different purposes

For items I9 through I12, we classified the primary study data by identifying the primary studies’ research themes. These themes were identified through the guidelines proposed by Braun et al. [5] to conduct thematic analysis in documents. Thematic analysis corresponds to a method of searching for repeated patterns of meanings over a data set (e.g., text). It is a method adaptable to the context and allows for collaborative discussion to identify themes. A *theme* captures something important about the data concerning the research topic (in our study, tactics). The steps executed to identify themes are as follows:

- *Search of themes*: This step aims to identify the main features that allow answering the research questions. The features are characterized in concrete sentences.
- *Theme review*: Two authors and one contributor review the identified topics. This review is focused on verifying whether the theme effectively characterizes an answer to a research question. More precisely, this step checks that the identified topic is unambiguous and precise, as far as possible.
- *Define and name the themes*: Once the themes are reviewed, this step names and defines the themes.

The theme identification method was used to tabulate I10, I11, and I12. Regarding I13, the identification of new or updated taxonomies is performed through the analysis of each selected study.

3 Dissemination of results

In this section, we describe our plan for the publication of the results.

- The main results will be published in a journal (WoS, Q1) specialized in software.
- We will publish a repository where we will describe the review protocol and the results obtained in order to promote the replication of our study.
- Depending on the results, we will describe the results in practitioner-oriented venues to introduce architecture tactics in the industry.

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